

Germplasm improvement

Genetics

Loci for hybrid sterility in Basmati crosses

Jianmin Wan, Nanjing Agricultural University, Nanjing, 210095, China; H. Ikehashi, Faculty of Agriculture, Kyoto University, Kyoto 606-1, Japan

Massive screening has been conducted in hybrid rice breeding to determine if a set of varieties can be used as maintainers or restorers. If the pollen of an F₁ hybrid between a cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) tester and any given variety is sterile, the variety may be used as maintainer. If the pollen is sound and the panicles of the F₁ are

completely fertile, the variety may be used as a restorer. However, interference of hybrid sterility genes with a CMS-restoration factor system very much confounds the criteria used in the screening.

Hybrid sterility in indica-japonica crosses is due to an allelic interaction at a gamete abortion locus, *S-5*, on chromosome 6. Recently, in other groups of rice hybrids, similar allelic interactions were found at loci *S-7* on chromosome 4, *S-8* on chromosome 6, *S-9* on chromosome 7, and *S-15* on chromosome 12. All of them cause sterility independent of the others.

We found hybrid sterility loci in crosses with Basmati 370, the derivatives of which are frequently used in hybrid rice breeding. Basmati 370 showed hybrid sterility in its

crosses to several tester varieties. Spikelet fertility levels in some of the crosses were 67.2% in Basmati 370/IR36, 61.3% in Basmati 370/IR2061-628, 62.8% in Basmati 370/IR2061-418, and 43.2% in Basmati 370/Akihikari. The F₁ hybrid of Basmati 370/Ketan Nangka (wide compatibility variety) showed normal fertility of 90.1%.

Marker alleles at each of the hybrid sterility loci were identified (Table 1). Basmati 370 is closer to japonicas in terms of its isozymes, therefore it is genetically diverse from indicas and should result in pronounced hybrid vigor in its crosses with indicas.

The marker genotypes that differentiated the level of spikelet fertility in segregating populations were determined (Table 2).

When Basmati 370 was crossed with major indica varieties, such as IR36 and IR2061-628, hybrid sterility was revealed due to an allelic interaction at *S-8*. In the cross Basmati 370/IR2061-418, hybrid sterility was due to an allelic interaction at *S-7*. In Basmati 370/Akihikari (a japonica tester), hybrid sterility was affected by at least the alleles at *S-5*.

We believe that the difficulties in using Basmati 370 in hybrid rice breeding programs are caused by its allelic interactions at several hybrid sterility loci. Systematic use of neutral alleles at each locus is recommended to solve the problem. ■

Table 1. Varieties used and their marker alleles at respective loci.^a

Parent	Marker allele and chromosome						
	Chromosome 6		Chromosome 7		Chromosome 4	Chromosome 12	Chromosome 1
	<i>Est-2</i> (<i>S-5</i>)	<i>Amp-3</i>	<i>Cat-1</i> (<i>S-8</i>)	<i>Est-9</i> (<i>S-7</i>)	<i>Est-1</i> (<i>S-9</i>)	<i>Sdh-1</i> (<i>S-15</i>)	<i>Est-5^b</i> (<i>S-16</i>)
Basmati 370	1	1	2	1	0	2	2
Akihikari	0	1	2	1	0	2	1
IR36	2	1	1	2	1	1	1
IR2061-628	2	1	1	2	1	1	1
IR2061-418	2	1	1	2	1	1	1
Gilchao 2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1
Ketan Nangka	1	2	2	1	0	2	1

^aThe isozyme allele systems are from Morishima and Glaszmann (1991). ^bThree hybrid sterility loci are shown under the marker loci.

Table 2. Distribution of spikelet fertility classified by marker genotype of hybrids between Basmati 370 and IRRI lines or a japonica test line.^a

Genotype	Number of plants in spikelet fertility										Total mean	T-test
	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100		
<i>Basmati 370/IR36/IR36</i>												
<i>Cat-1²/Cat-1¹</i>	2	3	3	5	9	10	3	3	<u>2</u>	0	40 ^{**b}	52.3 ^{**}
<i>Cat-1¹/Cat-1¹</i>	<u>2</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>17</u>	<u>18</u>	16	61	75.8
SF was not differentiated at <i>Est-2</i> , <i>Est-9</i> , <i>Est-1</i> , <i>Sdh-1</i> and <i>Est-5</i>												
<i>Basmati 370/IR2061-628/Basmati 370</i>												
<i>Cat-1²/Cat-1²</i>	1	<u>1</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>1</u>	0	<u>2</u>	8	10	8	6	38 ^{**}	76.3 ^{**}
<i>Cat-1¹/Cat-1²</i>	3	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>4</u>	7	<u>9</u>	8	<u>8</u>	<u>8</u>	<u>4</u>	55	51.7
SF was not differentiated at <i>Est-2</i> , <i>Est-9</i> , <i>Est-1</i> , <i>Sdh-1</i> , and <i>Est-5</i>												
<i>Basmati 370/IR2061-418/Basmati 370</i>												
<i>Est-9²/Est-9¹</i>	2	2	3	3	6	3	14	8	<u>5</u>	<u>4</u>	50 ^{**}	56.3 ^{**}
<i>Est-9¹/Est-9¹</i>	1	1	1	2	1	1	4	10	10	6	37	74.3
SF was not differentiated at <i>Est-2</i> , <i>Cat-1</i> , <i>Est-1</i> , <i>Sdh-1</i> , and <i>Est-5</i>												
<i>Basmati 370/Ketan Nangka/Akihikari</i>												
<i>Amp-3²/Amp-3¹</i>	0	<u>1</u>	0	0	<u>3</u>	<u>2</u>	14	11	7	5	43	76.5 ^{**}
<i>Amp-3¹/Amp-3¹</i>	2	<u>1</u>	2	3	4	2	<u>4</u>	<u>7</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>3</u>	33	52.3

^aNumbers underlined are assumed to be recombinants. ^b** = significant at the 1% level.